

EFFECTIVE WAYS TO CONDUCT CIRCLE LESSONS IN ELEMENTARY GRADES OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Akbarova D.M.

English teacher of the 37th general secondary school under the jurisdiction of SandBSO,
Koshrabot district, Samarkand region

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Abstract. *This article shows how to organize group activities, which are part of extracurricular activities, how important they are in students' activities, and how to organize them.*

Keywords: *circle, process, education, method, pedagogy, order, discipline, school, science.*

Conducting circle training using interactive methods will further improve the quality of Education. The child should be able to think freely in training, openly demonstrate his creativity. In the circle, it is necessary to create conditions for a child to have meaningful free time after school lessons. Circle training allows the child to work on himself, be able to engage in the direction in which he is interested, have additional knowledge. During the training, together with the lesson, children Exchange creative experiences with each other. Looking in one direction, future young specialists are formed. A circle can replace a circle according to the fact that children freely choose the circles themselves, attend several circles at the same time and are interested. This will serve as a starting step in the choice of children for some profession in the future.[3]

Behavioral training is more complex than mind training. Students can understand the essence of requirements well, but in most cases do not comply with them. Therefore, practicing it independently makes cultural behavior more habitual. In the process of imposing requirements, it is necessary to establish control over the implementation of students. Control is carried out using various conditions, maintaining, behavioral journal, recording scores for classroom shifts, etc. Control should be true regular. It is necessary to warn the readers of its results. Organizing and gendering the team. [7,8] It is closely related to the training of activists. The formation of team activists depends on the content of the team's need for one or another activity. To identify community activists, it is necessary for the teacher to monitor the activities of students, their participation in team work, behavior, determine the competence of each student to organize social activities. The composition of team activists is purposeful if the children themselves, of course, are selected with the participation and guidance of an educator. In this case, it is necessary to assign a specific task to each member of the pedagogical community activists, to achieve their reporting on these tasks in a certain period. The deputy director of spiritual and educational affairs of the school embodies qualities that are able to behave with affection and love towards students, demanding towards the pedagogical community and parents, and regularly work on themselves, be patient, carefully articulate their thoughts and attract others.[2]

One of the types of extracurricular activities in order to properly organize students free time, circle training is important in the life of students. In the training of the circle, their shells of creativity are further developed. This article considers the issue of organizing circle training, which is a kind of extracurricular activity, and developing shells of creativity for students in training. Different circles are found in the work experience of schools. Among interdisciplinary circles, the

most common are physical-technical, technical creativity circles. The meaning of the activities of students in these circles comes from the name of the circle itself. In technical-creative circles, the objects of labor of students are usually different models. In this, students manage to clarify with examples certain laws that are studied in the science of technology, which helps in mastering the basics of science. On the other hand, students design and create a model construct. Physico-technical circles are led at the same time by teachers of physics and technology. Non-science circles are now more common in extracurricular work. According to the content of the activities of students, these circles can be diverse. In this case, it goes only about circles in addition to such a subject that for their work, the school workshops are used as a material base, or the activities of students rely on the knowledge and qualifications gained in the lessons of technology. Employees of the base enterprise, parents are often invited to lead non-fan circles. And the teacher gives them methodological assistance. The content of the work of circles is determined in programs. These programs are developed by methodological cabinets under public education, as well as young technicians. The programs will be for one and two academic years. Circle training usually takes place once a week for two hours.[1]

From the point of view of connection with academic disciplines, circles can be divided into three groups into interdisciplinary, interdisciplinary and non-disciplinary circles. It is said that circles on science are those that are directly related to Labor Education. According to its content, these circles are an ostensibly continuation of the work performed by students in a technology lesson, but in this, the activities of students will be more complex, wider. Science circles should not simply repeat what students originally did. Among interdisciplinary circles, the most common are physical-technical, technical creativity circles. The meaning of the activities of students in these circles comes from the name of the circle itself. In technical-creative circles, the objects of labor of students are usually different models. In this, students manage to clarify with examples certain laws that are studied in the science of technology, which helps in mastering the basics of science. On the other hand, students design and create a model construct. Physico-technical circles are led at the same time by teachers of physics and technology. Non-science circles are now more common in extracurricular work. According to the content of the activities of students, these circles can be diverse. In this case, it goes only about circles in addition to such a subject that for their work, school workshops are used as a material base, or the activities of students rely on the knowledge and qualifications gained in the lessons of technology. [5,6]

Employees of the base enterprise, parents are often invited to lead non-fan circles. And the teacher provides them with methodological support. The content of the work of circles is determined in programs. These programs are developed by methodological cabinets under public education, as well as young technicians. The programs will be for one and two academic years. Circle training usually takes place once a week for two hours. However, it is also common among readers to be unsatisfied with it. More training is possible with them, but for this it is necessary to agree with the head of the class, since he knows perfectly well how each student will master other subjects. There should be no more than 15 students in one circle, otherwise it will be difficult to lead each of them individually. The work experience of advanced schools shows that the structure of the circle machine based on school workshops stands close to the combined (mixed) lesson structure.

This is due to the fact that in any circle training, a number of didactic issues are usually solved. The preparation of a specific object of Labor is seen by students as the main goal pursued by the training of the circle.[2]

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